

Design and *in silico* study of thiourea–pyrazolopyrimidine hybrids as dual PI3K/mTOR inhibitors for cancer therapy

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Received 28 September 2025 ♦ Accepted 18 January 2026 ♦ Published 2 February 2026

Citation: Ruswanto R, Nofianti T, Mardaningrum R, Kesuma D, Fajriah S, Aulia AR, Zahwa SF, Handirana ZP (2026) Design and *in silico* study of thiourea–pyrazolopyrimidine hybrids as dual PI3K/mTOR inhibitors for cancer therapy. *Pharmacia* 73: 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e173385>

Abstract

Background: Cancer remains a major cause of mortality worldwide, with the PI3K/mTOR signaling pathway playing a crucial role in tumor progression, proliferation, and therapeutic resistance. Although several dual PI3K/mTOR inhibitors have been developed, their clinical outcomes remain limited due to poor bioavailability, significant toxicities, and rapid resistance. Molecular hybridization offers a rational strategy to address these limitations by integrating multiple pharmacophores into a single scaffold.

Aim: This study aimed to design and evaluate thiourea–pyrazolopyrimidine hybrids as potential dual PI3K/mTOR inhibitors using *in silico* approaches, supported by the preliminary synthesis of precursor molecules.

Materials and methods: Eighty hybrid compounds were generated using ChemDraw and MarvinSketch, optimized by energy minimization, and docked against PI3K (PDB ID: 3L54) and mTOR (PDB ID: 4JT6) using AutoDock 4.2. The best candidates were further validated through 30 ns molecular dynamics (MD) simulations using Desmond, while pharmacokinetic and toxicity properties were assessed using pkCSM.

Results: Several derivatives, particularly 2-phenylbenzoate and 4-thiophen analogs, demonstrated stronger binding affinities than native ligands, supported by stable hydrogen bonding and hydrophobic interactions. MD simulations confirmed the stability of the complexes, with RMSD and RMSF values indicating consistent conformations throughout the trajectory. ADMET predictions suggested favorable absorption, low CYP450 inhibition, and reduced mutagenic potential, especially for CF₃ and lipophilic substituents.

Conclusion: In conclusion, thiourea–pyrazolopyrimidine hybrids exhibit promising dual PI3K/mTOR inhibitory potential with enhanced pharmacokinetic and safety profiles compared to lead compounds. These results establish a solid foundation for further synthesis, characterization, and biological evaluation as novel anticancer candidates.

Keywords

Anticancer, dual PI3K/mTOR inhibitor, *in silico*, synthesis, thiourea–pyrazolopyrimidine hybrids

Introduction

Cancer remains one of the leading causes of mortality worldwide, with incidence rates continuing to rise each year. Recent global statistics underscore its critical impact, positioning cancer as one of the most pressing public health challenges of the 21st century (Siegel et al. 2023). Among the key signaling pathways implicated in tumor progression, the phosphatidylinositol 3-kinase/mammalian target of rapamycin (PI3K/mTOR) axis plays a central role in regulating cell growth, proliferation, metabolism, and survival. Dysregulation of this pathway is strongly associated with tumorigenesis and the emergence of resistance to conventional therapies (Porta et al. 2014; Janku et al. 2018).

Over the past decade, several PI3K/mTOR inhibitors have been developed, including BEZ235 (dactolisib), GDC-0980, and PF-04691502, which initially demonstrated promising dual-target activity. However, these agents are limited by poor bioavailability, dose-limiting toxicities, and the rapid emergence of drug resistance, significantly hampering their clinical utility (Sabbah et al. 2011; Janku et al. 2018; Gao et al. 2023). Consequently, multi-target inhibition strategies are increasingly recognized as more effective therapeutic approaches than single-target inhibition, offering the potential for improved selectivity, reduced toxicity, and enhanced metabolic stability (Kucuksayan and Ozben 2017; Gontijo et al. 2020, 2020; Szumilak et al. 2021; Wang and Tortorella 2022).

In this context, thiourea derivatives have emerged as a class of compounds with notable anticancer potential. Several 1-benzoyl-3-methylthiourea derivatives have been synthesized and reported to induce apoptosis, inhibit cancer cell proliferation, and modulate oncogenic signaling pathways, although their therapeutic application remains constrained by poor selectivity and cytotoxicity (Ruswanto and Siswando 2015; Ruswanto et al. 2017, 2018, 2021, 2023a). In contrast, pyrazolopyrimidines represent a privileged heterocyclic scaffold with a well-documented affinity for the ATP-binding domain of PI3K/mTOR, making them attractive structural motifs for inhibitor design (Sabbah et al. 2011; Lee et al. 2013; Welker and Kulik 2013).

A rational approach to overcome these limitations is molecular hybridization, which involves the integration of two pharmacophores into a single hybrid entity. This strategy has been successfully applied in the design of multi-target drug candidates, yielding molecules with synergistic biological effects, improved pharmacokinetic properties, and reduced resistance profiles compared to single agents (Kucuksayan and Ozben 2017; Gontijo et al. 2020; Szumilak et al. 2021). Accordingly, the development of thiourea–pyrazolopyrimidine hybrids holds considerable promise, as such molecules may combine the anticancer potential of thioureas with the high affinity of pyrazolopyrimidines toward PI3K/mTOR, thereby enhancing hydrophobic interactions, binding affinity, and metabolic stability while reducing toxicity (Lee et al. 2013; Huang et al. 2022).

To rationalize this drug design, *in silico* approaches provide a powerful and cost-effective strategy. Computational methods such as molecular docking are widely employed to evaluate ligand–protein binding affinities (Jain and Gupta 2023), while molecular dynamics (MD) simulations allow for the assessment of the stability of ligand–target complexes under physiological conditions (Ruswanto et al. 2023b). In addition, *in silico* pharmacokinetic and toxicity predictions (ADMET) serve as essential preliminary filters in early drug discovery, providing valuable insights into drug-likeness and safety profiles (Pires et al. 2015). Collectively, these approaches support the rational design and virtual evaluation of novel thiourea–pyrazolopyrimidine hybrids as potential dual PI3K/mTOR inhibitors for the treatment of cancer.

The novelty of this study lies in the rational hybridization of thiourea and pyrazolopyrimidine pharmacophores into a single molecular scaffold specifically optimized for dual PI3K/mTOR inhibition. Unlike previously reported single-scaffold or loosely related analogs, the proposed hybrids demonstrate enhanced binding affinity, improved interaction stability, and more favorable predicted pharmacokinetic profiles. Notably, several top-ranked hybrids exhibited superior binding free energy and stability compared to reference ligands while maintaining acceptable ADMET characteristics. These findings highlight the advantage of the hybrid design strategy in overcoming limitations associated with earlier PI3K/mTOR inhibitors and underscore the potential of thiourea–pyrazolopyrimidine hybrids as a distinct and promising class of anticancer candidates.

Materials and methods

Ligand preparation

Hybrid thiourea–pyrazolopyrimidine derivatives were designed using ChemDraw Ultra 20.0 and subsequently converted into three-dimensional structures. The geometry of each ligand was optimized using MarvinSketch 21.13, employing the MMFF94 force field until energy minimization was achieved. The minimized ligands were then saved in PDBQT format for docking simulations.

Protein preparation

The three-dimensional crystal structures of PI3K (PDB ID: 3L54) and mTOR (PDB ID: 4JT6) were retrieved from the Protein Data Bank (RCSB PDB). Protein preparation was carried out using AutoDockTools 1.5.7 by removing crystallographic water molecules, heteroatoms, and co-crystallized ligands, followed by the addition of polar hydrogen atoms and assignment of Kollman charges. The processed receptor structures were stored in PDBQT format.

Molecular docking was performed using AutoDock 4.2 with the Lamarckian Genetic Algorithm (LGA) as the search strategy. The docking grid was positioned at the

ATP-binding site of each receptor, with the grid box size adjusted to fully encompass the binding pocket (PI3K: center_x = 13.751, center_y = -4.126, center_z = 22.894; mTOR: center_x = 52.217, center_y = 31.844, center_z = 64.038; grid dimensions = 40 × 40 × 40 Å). Docking parameters included 100 runs, a population size of 150, a maximum of 2.5×10^6 energy evaluations, and 27,000 generations. Docking results were evaluated based on binding affinity (kcal/mol) and ligand–protein interactions such as hydrogen bonds, hydrophobic contacts, and π – π stacking. Both two- and three-dimensional interaction analyses were conducted using Discovery Studio Visualizer 2021 (Mardianingrum et al. 2021; Ruswanto et al. 2021).

Molecular dynamics (MD) simulation

The most promising complexes obtained from docking were further subjected to molecular dynamics (MD) simulations using Desmond (Schrödinger Release 2021, Academic Free License) with the OPLS_2005 force field. Each protein–ligand complex was solvated in an orthorhombic simulation box with a 10 Å buffer distance, using the TIP3P water model and 0.15 M NaCl to neutralize the system. Energy minimization was conducted for 100 ps to remove steric clashes, followed by equilibration under the NPT ensemble at 300 K and 1.01325 bar using the Nose–Hoover thermostat and Martyna–Tobias–Klein barostat (Renadi et al. 2023; Septian et al. 2023). Production runs were performed for 30 ns with a 2 fs integration time step, and trajectory frames were recorded every 1.2 ps. Analysis of the MD trajectories was performed using the Simulation Interaction Diagram (SID) tool in Desmond. The parameters assessed included root mean square deviation (RMSD) to monitor overall complex stability, root mean square fluctuation (RMSF) to examine residue flexibility, radius of gyration (rGyr) to assess protein compactness, hydrogen bond occupancy to evaluate interaction stability, and solvent accessible surface area (SASA) to investigate changes in solvent exposure throughout the simulation (Ruswanto et al. 2022, 2023a).

ADMET prediction

The pharmacokinetic and toxicity profiles of the designed hybrids were predicted using the pkCSM web server. Parameters such as intestinal absorption, blood–brain barrier (BBB) penetration, cytochrome P450 (CYP450) inhibition, mutagenicity (AMES test), and acute toxicity (LD_{50}) were evaluated to assess the drug-likeness and safety of the compounds (Pires et al. 2015; Silalahi et al. 2025).

Results and discussion

Although the present study is limited to *in silico* approaches, it provides a robust and rational framework for the early-stage discovery of dual PI3K/mTOR inhibitors. Computational methods such as molecular docking, molecular

dynamics simulations, and ADMET prediction are widely recognized as effective tools for prioritizing lead compounds before costly and time-consuming experimental studies. The identified thiourea–pyrazolopyrimidine hybrids demonstrated favorable binding affinity, stable interactions with key active-site residues, and acceptable predicted pharmacokinetic and safety profiles, supporting their potential as promising lead candidates. Future work will focus on the chemical synthesis of the top-ranked compounds, followed by *in vitro* evaluation against relevant cancer cell lines and subsequent *in vivo* studies to validate their biological activity, mechanism of action, and therapeutic potential.

In this study, 80 hybrid compounds were designed from thiourea derivatives and pyrazolopyrimidine compounds drawn using MarvinSketch 5.2.5.1, with lead compounds shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Design structure of the proposed hybrid compound.

Before molecular docking and molecular dynamics simulations were performed, the designed compounds were prepared in two stages. First, the ligands were cleaned in 2D format, protonated at physiological blood pH (7.4), and saved in .mrv format. Second, ligand energy minimization was performed, and the structures were saved in .pdb format. Both ligand preparation stages were conducted using MarvinSketch software.

Pharmacokinetic and toxicity predictions

Pharmacokinetic and toxicity profiles are used in the research and development of new drugs to evaluate the effectiveness and potential side effects of drug candidates and are assessed using <https://biosig.lab.uq.edu.au/pkcsml/>. This assessment depends on a number of parameters, such as Caco-2, intestinal absorption, VDss, BBB, activity as a substrate and inhibitor of CYP3A4, OCT2, AMES toxicity, hepatotoxicity, and LD50. Tables 1, 2 present the predicted pharmacokinetic and toxicity profiles based on these parameters, providing an overview of the potential performance and risks associated with the test ligands.

Based on the results of pkCSM predictions (Pires et al. 2015), in general, the majority of derivative compounds exhibit fairly good pharmacokinetic profiles. In terms of absorption, most compounds show Caco-2 permeability

Table 1. Pharmacokinetic properties of the Cs.

No.	Substituent	Pharmacokinetic Properties					
		Absorption		Distribution		Metabolism	Excretion
		Caco2 permeability	Intestinal absorption (human)	VDss (human)	BBB permeability	CYP2D6 inhibitor	Renal OCT2 substrate
1	4-phenyldiazen	0.604	96.846	-0.381	-0.793	No	No
2	4-chloromethyl	0.997	95.328	-0.536	-0.688	No	No
3	4-dimethylamino	1.093	97.943	-0.590	-0.670	No	No
4	2-chloromethyl	0.900	93.987	-0.594	-0.683	No	No
5	3-CF3	0.982	94.225	-0.719	-0.932	No	No
6	3-phenyl acetat	0.270	82.309	-0.947	-0.919	No	No
7	4-methylthio	1.045	96.189	-0.556	-0.721	No	No
8	2-CF3	1.084	94.129	-0.906	-0.909	No	No
9	3-OCF3	1.088	93.919	-1.074	-1.149	No	No
10	4-trifluoromethylthio	1.060	92.567	-0.910	-1.104	No	No
11	4-trifluoromethoxy	1.088	93.919	-1.074	-1.149	No	No
12	4-sulfonylchloride	-0.071	83.367	-1.267	-1.125	No	No
13	4-difluoromethylthio	1.054	93.698	-0.815	-0.983	No	No
14	4-difluoromethoxy	1.082	95.050	-0.979	-1.028	No	No
15	3,5-CF3	1.088	90.856	-1.054	-1.346	No	No
16	2-F, 5-CF3	1.311	97.441	0.997	0.806	No	No
17	2,5-CF3	1.088	90.856	-1.054	-1.346	No	No
18	2-CF3, 4-F	1.082	93.371	-1.074	-1.110	No	No
19	2-F, 4-CF3	1.082	93.371	-1.074	-1.110	No	No
20	3-F, 4-CF3	1.082	93.371	-1.074	-1.110	No	No
21	2-F, 3-CF3	1.082	93.371	-1.074	-1.110	No	No
22	2-CF3, 5-F	1.082	93.371	-1.074	-1.110	No	No
23	2,4-CF3	1.088	90.856	-1.054	-1.346	No	No
24	2,6-CF3	1.088	90.856	-1.054	-1.346	No	No
25	2-Cl, 4-CF3	1.067	92.469	-0.940	-1.077	No	No
26	3,5-Cl 4-OCH3	1.061	94.077	-0.963	-1.036	No	No
27	2-F, 3-Cl, 5-CF3	1.064	91.710	-1.106	-1.278	No	No
28	2-F, 3-Cl, 6-CF3	1.064	91.710	-1.106	-1.278	No	No
29	3-F, 5-CF3	1.311	97.441	0.997	0.806	No	No
30	3-Cl, 6-CF3	1.067	92.469	-0.940	-1.077	No	No
31	4-thiadiazol	0.204	90.665	-1.299	-1.073	No	No
32	3-CF3, 4-CH3	1.089	93.927	-0.874	-0.902	No	No
33	4-pyrazol	1.155	97.421	-1.116	-0.830	No	No
34	4-bromomethyl	1.069	95.844	-0.725	-0.665	No	No
35	2,3,4,5,6-F	1.068	93.609	-1.551	-1.476	No	No
36	2-phenylbenzoate	0.741	89.285	-0.551	-0.726	No	No
37	4-ethyl	1.011	96.402	-0.476	-0.517	No	No
38	2-CN	0.265	85.492	-0.832	-0.694	No	No
39	3-CN	0.265	85.492	-0.832	-0.694	No	No
40	4-CN	0.265	85.492	-0.832	-0.694	No	No
41	4-propyl	0.991	95.675	-0.354	-0.483	No	No
42	4-I	1.061	95.714	-0.658	-0.747	No	No
43	4-butyl	0.985	95.256	-0.263	-0.487	No	No
44	4-heptyl	0.593	94.260	0.094	-0.475	No	No
45	4-hexyl	0.940	94.601	-0.013	-0.470	No	No
46	4-octyl	0.961	94.577	-0.293	-0.629	No	No
47	4-decyl	0.943	93.739	-0.164	-0.677	No	No
48	4-butoxy	1.087	96.142	-0.704	-0.772	No	No
49	2,4-CH3	1.089	96.998	-0.684	-0.457	No	No
50	2,4-F	1.075	95.885	-1.082	-0.873	No	No
51	3,4-F	1.075	95.885	-1.082	-0.873	No	No
52	2,4,6-CH3	1.093	96.796	-0.652	-0.450	No	No
53	2,4,5-F	1.073	95.127	-1.244	-1.074	No	No

No.	Substituent	Pharmacokinetic Properties					
		Absorption		Distribution		Metabolism	Excretion
		Caco2 permeability	Intestinal absorption (human)	VDss (human)	BBB permeability	CYP2D6 inhibitor	Renal OCT2 substrate
54	3-NO ₂ , 4-Cl	0.081	86.147	-1.111	-1.168	No	No
55	3,4,5-F	1.073	95.127	-1.244	-1.074	No	No
56	2-Cl, 4-NO ₂	0.081	86.147	-1.111	-1.168	No	No
57	2,4,6-Cl	1.028	92.420	-0.856	-0.976	No	No
58	3,4-OCH ₃	1.113	97.396	-1.024	-0.928	No	No
59	3,4,5-OCH ₃	0.248	83.049	-1.161	-1.157	No	No
60	2,4-NO ₂	0.085	81.997	-1.361	-1.529	No	No
61	2,4-OCH ₃	1.113	97.396	-1.024	-0.928	No	No
62	3-NO ₂ , 4-CH ₃	0.193	85.439	-1.041	-0.993	No	No
63	2-Cl, 4-F	1.060	94.983	-0.955	-0.840	No	No
64	3, CH ₃ , 4-F	1.082	96.442	-0.885	-0.665	No	No
65	2,3,4,5-F	1.070	94.368	-1.401	-1.275	No	No
66	2,3,4,6-F	1.070	94.368	-1.401	-1.275	No	No
67	2,6-F, 4-OCH ₃	1.091	95.882	-1.217	-1.102	No	No
68	3,5-Cl, 4-OCH ₃	1.061	94.077	-0.996	-1.036	No	No
69	2,4-F,3-Cl	1.058	94.225	-1.120	-1.042	No	No
70	3-Cl, 4-F	1.060	94.983	-0.955	-0.840	No	No
71	3-F, 4-OCH ₃	1.094	96.641	-1.053	-0.901	No	No
72	3-F, 4-CH ₃	1.082	96.442	-0.885	-0.665	No	No
73	2-F, 4-Br	1.056	94.916	-0.943	-0.849	No	No
74	3-CH ₃ , 4-Br	1.063	95.472	-0.742	-0.641	No	No
75	2,5-F, 4-Cl	1.058	94.225	-1.120	-1.042	No	No
76	3-CF ₃ , 4-F	1.311	97.441	0.997	0.806	No	No
77	4-sulfonylfluoride	-0.075	83.293	-1.284	-1.234	No	No
78	4-thiophen	1.130	95.107	-0.889	-0.632	No	No
79	Naphthoyl	1.137	96.635	-0.814	-0.437	No	No
80	Lead compound	1.081	97.403	-0.744	-0.471	No	No

Table 2. Toxicity profile.

No	Substituent	Toxicity		
		AMES toxicity	Oral Rat Acute Toxicity (LD50)	Hepatotoxicity
1	4-phenyldiazene	Mutagen	2.433	Yes
2	4-chloromethyl	Non-mutagen	2.720	Yes
3	4-dimethylamino	Non-mutagen	2.822	Yes
4	2-chloromethyl	Non-mutagen	2.745	Yes
5	3-CF ₃	Non-mutagen	2.887	Yes
6	3-phenyl acetate	Non-mutagen	2.801	Yes
7	4-methylthio	Non-mutagen	2.864	Yes
8	2-CF ₃	Non-mutagen	3.079	Yes
9	3-OCF ₃	Non-mutagen	3.032	Yes
10	4-trifluoromethylthio	Non-mutagen	3.203	Yes
11	4-trifluoromethoxy	Non-mutagen	3.032	Yes
12	4-sulfonylchloride	Mutagen	2.705	Yes
13	4-difluoromethylthio	Non-mutagen	3.139	Yes
14	4-difluoromethoxy	Mutagen	2.951	Yes
15	3,5-CF ₃	Non-mutagen	3.259	Yes
16	2-F, 5-CF ₃	Non-mutagen	2.089	No
17	2,5-CF ₃	Non-mutagen	3.259	Yes
18	2-CF ₃ , 4-F	Non-mutagen	3.082	Yes
19	2-F, 4-CF ₃	Non-mutagen	3.082	Yes
20	3-F, 4-CF ₃	Non-mutagen	3.082	Yes
21	2-F, 3-CF ₃	Non-mutagen	3.082	Yes
22	2-CF ₃ , 5-F	Non-mutagen	3.082	Yes
23	2,4-CF ₃	Non-mutagen	3.259	Yes

No	Substituent	Toxicity		
		AMES toxicity	Oral Rat Acute Toxicity (LD50)	Hepatotoxicity
24	2,6-CF3	Non-mutagen	3.259	Yes
25	2-Cl, 4-CF3	Non-mutagen	3.184	Yes
26	3,5-Cl 4-OCH3	Non-mutagen	2.987	No
27	2-F, 3-Cl, 5-CF3	Non-mutagen	3.172	Yes
28	2-F, 3-Cl, 6-CF3	Non-mutagen	3.172	Yes
29	3-F, 5-CF3	Non-mutagen	2.089	No
30	3-Cl, 6-CF3	Non-mutagen	3.184	Yes
31	4-thiadiazol	Mutagen	2.822	Yes
32	3-CF3, 4-CH3	Non-mutagen	3.097	Yes
33	4-pyrazol	Mutagen	2.819	Yes
34	4-bromomethyl	Mutagen	2.359	Yes
35	2,3,4,5,6-F	Non-mutagen	2.837	Yes
36	2-phenylbenzoate	Non-mutagen	2.949	Yes
37	4-ethyl	Non-mutagen	2.819	Yes
38	2-CN	Non-mutagen	2.811	Yes
39	3-CN	Non-mutagen	2.811	Yes
40	4-CN	Non-mutagen	2.811	Yes
41	4-propyl	Non-mutagen	2.800	Yes
42	4-I	Non-mutagen	2.785	No
43	4-butyl	Non-mutagen	2.775	Yes
44	4-heptyl	Non-mutagen	2.767	Yes
45	4-hexyl	Non-mutagen	2.768	Yes
46	4-octyl	Non-mutagen	2.712	Yes
47	4-decyl	Non-mutagen	2.662	Yes
48	4-butoxy	Non-mutagen	2.752	Yes
49	2,4-CH3	Mutagen	2.763	Yes
50	2,4-F	Mutagen	2.775	Yes
51	3,4-F	Mutagen	2.775	Yes
52	2,4,6-CH3	Non-mutagen	2.792	Yes
53	2,4,5-F	Mutagen	2.803	Yes
54	3-NO2, 4-Cl	Mutagen	2.463	No
55	3,4,5-F	Mutagen	2.803	Yes
56	2-Cl, 4-NO2	Mutagen	2.463	No
57	2,4,6-Cl	Non-mutagen	3.153	No
58	3,4-OCH3	Mutagen	2.650	Yes
59	3,4,5-OCH3	Mutagen	2.603	Yes
60	2,4-NO2	Mutagen	2.289	Yes
61	2,4-OCH3	Mutagen	2.650	Yes
62	3-NO2, 4-CH3	Mutagen	2.394	Yes
63	2-Cl, 4-F	Mutagen	2.907	Yes
64	3, CH3, 4-F	Mutagen	2.772	Yes
65	2,3,4,5-F	Mutagen	1.824	Yes
66	2,3,4,6-F	Mutagen	1.824	Yes
67	2,6-F, 4-OCH3	Mutagen	2.744	Yes
68	3,5-Cl, 4-OCH3	Non-mutagen	2.987	No
69	2,4-F,3-Cl	Non-mutagen	2.927	Yes
70	3-Cl, 4-F	Mutagen	2.907	Yes
71	3-F, 4-OCH3	Mutagen	2.716	Yes
72	3-F, 4-CH3	Mutagen	2.772	Yes
73	2-F, 4-Br	Mutagen	2.908	Yes
74	3-CH3, 4-Br	Non-mutagen	2.906	Yes
75	2,5-F, 4-Cl	Non-mutagen	2.927	Yes
76	3-CF3, 4-F	Non-mutagen	2.089	No
77	4-sulfonylfluoride	Mutagen	2.684	Yes
78	4-thiophen	Non-mutagen	2.869	Yes
79	Naphthoyl	Mutagen	2.761	Yes
80	Lead compound	Mutagen	1.701	Yes

above the threshold of 0.9 log Papp and human intestinal absorption rates above 90%, indicating that compounds with moderate lipophilic substituents such as short alkyl groups and trifluoromethyl (CF₃) groups have the potential for good oral bioavailability. Conversely, compounds with large polar substituents such as NO₂ and SO₂Cl show reduced absorption capacity, with values < 82%, making them less ideal for further development. In terms of distribution, the volume of distribution (VDss) values are mostly negative (approximately –0.3 to –1.5 log L/kg), indicating a tendency for the compound to remain in plasma rather than in tissues.

Interestingly, long aliphatic substituents (e.g., 4-heptyl, 4-octyl, and 4-decyl) produced VDss values close to neutral, indicating increased distribution to tissues. For blood–brain barrier (BBB) penetration, most compounds show negative values (< –0.5 log BB) and are therefore unlikely to penetrate the brain, except for some CF₃ and fluorine derivatives (e.g., 2,5-F-5-CF₃ and 3-CF₃, 4-F) that have positive values close to 0.8, making them potentially capable of targeting the central nervous system. From a metabolic perspective, all compounds are predicted not to inhibit the CYP2D6 enzyme, which is an important advantage as it reduces the risk of drug interactions. Furthermore, none of the compounds are substrates for the renal transporter OCT2, suggesting that elimination is likely to depend more on hepatic metabolism than renal excretion. Overall, this analysis confirms that compounds with trifluoromethyl substituents and fluorine derivatives are more promising due to their combination of high absorption, better distribution, and BBB penetration for brain targeting, while compounds with large polar substituents should be eliminated from drug design priorities.

The toxicity prediction results (Table 2) indicate that the lead compound has an unfavorable profile because it is identified as mutagenic (positive AMES test) and hepatotoxic and has a relatively low oral rat LD₅₀ value (1.701 mol/kg), which indicates a higher level of acute toxicity than most of its derivatives.

Certain groups such as azo, nitro, sulfonyl, and heterocyclic (pyrazole and thiazole) are strongly associated with mutagenic properties. These findings are consistent with the literature, in which azo and nitro groups are often identified as structural alerts that can potentially cause mutagenesis through the formation of reactive metabolites (Mortelmans and Zeiger 2000; Kazius et al. 2005). Conversely, most trifluoromethyl (–CF₃, –OCF₃) and long-chain alkyl (butyl to decyl) substituents were identified as non-mutagenic, with higher LD₅₀ values (>3.0 mol/kg), making them relatively safer in terms of acute toxicity. This is consistent with reports that the addition of fluorine groups and lipophilic substituents can increase metabolic stability and reduce the risk of toxic bioactivation (Purser et al. 2008).

However, predictions of hepatotoxicity remain a concern because most compounds, including non-mutagenic derivatives, still show potential liver toxicity. Some substituents such as 2-F,5-CF₃; 3,5-Cl,4-OCH₃; and 2,4,6-Cl

are predicted to be non-hepatotoxic, suggesting that steric factors and electron-withdrawing properties may contribute to reducing the formation of hepatotoxic metabolites (Guengerich 2011). Therefore, these results imply that compound design optimization strategies should avoid high-risk groups (nitro, sulfonyl, and aromatic heterocycles) and instead utilize CF₃, OCF₃, or lipophilic alkyl substituents to obtain candidates with better safety profiles. Overall, these pkCSM prediction data can serve as a starting point for redesigning lead compounds using a structure–toxicity relationship approach before proceeding to *in vitro* and *in vivo* experimental validation.

Receptor analysis

In structure-based computational studies, receptor quality validation is an important step before further analyses such as molecular docking or molecular dynamics. One widely used platform is the SAVES server (Structural Analysis and Verification Server), which integrates various methods for assessing protein structure quality, including Ramachandran plot analysis to evaluate the distribution of ϕ - ψ torsion angles of residues and ERRAT analysis to examine non-bonded atom interaction patterns. This evaluation aims to ensure that protein structures obtained from databases such as the Protein Data Bank (PDB) have adequate geometry and stereochemical quality so that the results of computational simulations can be interpreted accurately and reliably (Ramachandran et al. 1963; Colovos and Yeates 1993).

***a.* Receptor PI3K (3L54.pdb)**

The PI3K receptor (PDB ID: 3L54) is one of the important molecular targets in cellular signaling pathways that play a role in regulating cell proliferation, differentiation, and survival. Before being used in further computational studies, the structure of this protein needs to be validated through quality testing using the SAVES server to ensure the reliability of its crystallographic data. Analysis using the Ramachandran plot and ERRAT provides an overview of the stereochemical quality and patterns of non-bonded atom interactions, thereby assessing the suitability of this model for use in *in silico* simulations such as molecular docking and molecular dynamics (Ramachandran et al. 1963; Colovos and Yeates 1993). The results are shown in Fig. 2.

The results of PI3K structure validation through the SAVES server (Fig. 2) show that 89.5% of residues are in the most favored regions of the Ramachandran plot, 10.1% are in additional allowed regions, and only 0.3% of residues (2 residues) fall into disallowed regions. Although slightly below the ideal standard of greater than 90%, this value still indicates good and acceptable geometric quality for computational studies, as the number of outlier residues is very small and likely located in flexible loop regions (Ramachandran et al. 1963). ERRAT2 analysis provides an overall quality factor of 94.9%, which is well above the 90% threshold and indicates global structural reliability (Colovos and Yeates 1993). Thus, the

PI3K structure is of fairly high quality and is suitable for advanced *in silico* analyses such as molecular docking and molecular dynamics.

b. Receptor mTOR (4JT6.pdb)

The mTOR receptor (PDB ID: 4JT6) is a key protein in the PI3K/Akt/mTOR pathway that regulates cell growth, metabolism, and survival and is an important target in cancer therapy. Before being used in computational studies, the structure of this protein was validated using the SAVES server to assess the quality of its geometry and atomic interactions. The results are shown in Fig. 3.

The results of mTOR protein structure validation using the SAVES server show that 84.5% of residues are in the most favored regions of the Ramachandran plot, 13.1% are in additional allowed regions, 1.5% are in generously allowed regions, and 0.9% of residues (23 residues) are identified in disallowed regions. This value is below the ideal quality standard (greater than 90% in the most favored regions), indicating some conformational instability, especially in loop or flexible domain areas (Ramachandran et al. 1963). ERRAT2 analysis supports these findings with an overall quality factor of 84.1%, which is lower than the high-quality standard (>90%) but still within the acceptable range for preliminary *in silico* analysis (Colovos and Yeates 1993). The presence of several high-error peaks on the ERRAT graph indicates potential local problems in non-bonded atom geometry, particularly in the residue segments around 1440, 1580, and 1620.

Overall, although this mTOR structure is not as robust as models with high Ramachandran and ERRAT scores, it can still be used in advanced computational studies such

as molecular docking and molecular dynamics, provided that refinement or energy minimization procedures are carried out to correct residues in disallowed regions. Thus, this structure is suitable for use, but the results of the study should be interpreted with caution, especially in domains that show quality anomalies.

Molecular docking

In molecular docking analysis using AutoDock, several key parameters are used to ensure the accuracy of ligand-receptor interaction predictions. The initial stage involves determining the grid box, which defines the ligand search area at the active site of the protein. For the PI3K receptor (PDB ID: 3L54), the grid box was set to $30 \times 40 \times 40$, with the grid center at coordinates (24.803, 15.683, 21.651) based on the position of the natural LXX ligand. Meanwhile, the mTOR receptor (PDB ID: 4JT6) used a grid box measuring $40 \times 40 \times 40$, with the grid center at coordinates (52.149, -0.071, -47.665), referring to the natural ligand X6K. Determining this grid is important to ensure that the docking process focuses on the relevant binding site.

Next, the docking results were analyzed based on root mean square deviation (RMSD), free energy of binding (FEB), and inhibition constant (Ki). The RMSD value reflects the stability of the docked ligand position relative to the reference ligand, FEB indicates the strength of the ligand-receptor interaction, and Ki provides an estimate of ligand inhibitory potential. In the docking results, the natural ligand on the PI3K receptor had an RMSD value of 1.266 Å, an FEB of -8.09 kcal/mol, and a Ki of 1.17 μM. In contrast, for the mTOR receptor, the RMSD was 0.389

Figure 2. Ramachandran plot and ERRAT test results of the PI3K receptor.

Figure 3. Ramachandran plot and ERRAT test results of the mTOR receptor.

Å, the FEB was -9.67 kcal/mol, and the K_i was 0.081 μM . These data indicate that the natural mTOR ligand binds more stably and has a higher affinity than the natural PI3K ligand and can therefore be used as a reference for evaluating the performance of hybrid compounds developed as dual PI3K/mTOR inhibitors (Morris et al. 2009; Trott and Olson 2010). The docking results for the PI3K receptor are shown in Table 3, and those for the mTOR receptor are shown in Table 4. The two-dimensional visualization of compound 78 (4-thiophen) with PI3K and mTOR is shown in Fig. 4.

The results of hybrid compound docking against the PI3K receptor (3L54), as shown in Table 3, indicate that several derivatives have stronger binding affinities than natural ligands. The 2-phenylbenzoate compound ranks highest, with a free energy of binding (FEB) value of -9.49 kcal/mol and an inhibition constant (K_i) of 0.111 μM , with hydrogen bond interactions at Val882 and Lys833, as well as hydrophobic bond support with key residues such as Met953, Ile963, Ile881, Asp964, and Tyr867.

The 4-thiadiazole and 2,4- NO_2 compounds also showed high affinity (FEB of -9.16 and -9.14 kcal/mol, respectively; K_i 0.192 – 0.198 μM), with interaction patterns involving the active residues Asp964, Val882, Tyr867, and Lys890, consistent with the binding pocket of natural ligands.

For comparison, the natural ligand on PI3K showed an FEB value of -8.09 kcal/mol with a K_i of 1.17 μM , interacting with residues Tyr867, Asp841, Asp964, Phe965, Lys833, Met953, Ile963, Ile879, Ile831, and Val882. This confirms that some hybrid compounds, especially 2-phenylbenzoate, have stronger bonds ($\Delta\text{FEB} \sim -1.4$ kcal/mol lower) and

greater inhibitory potential than natural ligands. Overall, these results indicate that structural modifications in hybrid compounds can enhance interactions with key residues in the PI3K active site, making them promising candidates for PI3K inhibitors in cancer therapy.

The docking results of hybrid compounds against the mTOR receptor (4JT6), as shown in Table 4, indicate that several derivatives are able to exceed the performance of natural ligands in terms of binding affinity. The 4-phenyldiazene and 2-CN compounds have the highest free energy of binding (FEB) values, respectively, of -10.07 kcal/mol, with an inhibition constant (K_i) of approximately 0.041 μM , which is better than the natural ligand, with an FEB of -9.67 kcal/mol and a K_i of 0.081 μM . Both show hydrogen bonding interactions with important residues in the mTOR binding site, including Asp2357, Cys2243, Val2240, Trp2239, Ile2237, and Tyr2225, and are reinforced by hydrophobic interactions with Met2345, Ile2356, and Leu2185.

In addition, the compounds 3,4,5- OCH_3 (-9.95 kcal/mol; K_i 0.099 μM) and 4-thiophen (-9.88 kcal/mol; K_i 0.057 μM) also showed consistent interactions with active residues, indicating their potential as potent inhibitors. This pattern confirms that aromatic substituents with electron-withdrawing groups and heteroaromatics can increase the affinity of ligands for mTOR.

In comparison, natural ligands interact with residues Val2240, Tyr2225, Asp2195, Met2345, Ile2237, Ile2356, and Trp2239, with lower binding affinities than the leading hybrid compound. This shows that the design of certain hybrid compounds is not only capable of maintaining key

Table 3. Docking results of the design hybrid compound against the PI3K receptor.

NO	Substituen	FEB (kcal/mol)	KI (μM)	RUN	INTERACTION	
					HYDROGEN BOND	HYDROPHOBIC BOND
36	2-phenylbenzoate	-9.49	0.1113	92	Val882, Lys833	Met953, Ile881, Ala885, Ile963, Asp964, Ile879, Lys833, Met804, Pro810, Tyr867
31	4-thiadiazol	-9.16	0.1929	24	Phe965, Asp964, Val882	Ile831, Ile879, Tyr867, Ile963, Val882, Phe961, Ala885, Met953, Ile881, Cys869, Asp964
60	2,4-NO ₂	-9.14	0.19854	65	Thr887, Lys890, Tyr867, Asp964	Met953, Phe961, Ile963, Ile831, Tyr867, Val882, Asp964
78	4-thiophen	-9.03	0.23906	83	Val882	Ala885, Met953, Ile881, Trp812, Asp964, Ile831, Asp841, Lys833, Ile879, Ile963, Tyr867, Val882
12	4-sulfonylchloride	-8.95	0.27455	62	Lys833,	Ile831, Ile963, Met953, Ala885, Tyr867, Ile881, Ile879, Asp964, Trp812, Val882
56	2-Cl, 4-NO ₂	-8.94	0.27953	94	Ala805, Lys890, Tyr867, Asp964	Met804, Lys833, Ile963, Ile879, Asp964
62	3-NO ₂ , 4-CH ₃	-8.94	0.28189	29	Lys890, Thr887, Thr867, Asp964	Met953, Met804, Trp812, Ile963, Ile879, Asp964
54	3-NO ₂ , 4-Cl	-8.91	0.29403	37	Thr887, Lys890, Tyr867, Asp964	Met953, Trp812, Ile879, Ile963, Asp964
59	3,4,5-OCH ₃	-8.88	0.31026	62	Val882, Tyr867, Lys833, Asp836, Asp841	Ile963, Ile879, Met953, Val882, Ile881, Ala885, Tyr867, Asp964
33	4-pyrazol	-8.8	0.35208	53	Val882, Asp836	Trp812, Ile881, Ala885, Met953, Val882, Tyr867, Ile963, Ile879, Lys833, Ile831, Asp964
79	naftoyl	-8.79	0.35976	39	Asp836, Lys833, Asp964, Val882	Asp964, Met953, Ile963, Phe961, Tyr867, Ile831, Ile879
6	3-phenyl acetat	-8.67	0.44417	2	Val882, Lys833	Asp841, Ile879, Ile963, Met953, Ala885, Ile881, Tyr867, Lys833, Asp964
74	3-CH ₃ , 4-Br	-8.66	0.44854	14	Val882	Tyr867, Met953, Ile963, Ile831, Ile879, Lys833, Asp964, Ile881, Ala885
42	4-I	-8.65	0.45599	62	Val882	Tyr867, Ile963, Asp964, Ile831, Ile879, Met853, Ile881, Ala885, Val882
44	4-heptyl	-8.56	0.5317	30	Asp836, Lys833, Tyr867, Asp964	Asp964, Ile879, Ile831, Tyr867, Ile963, Met953
77	4-sulfonylfluoride	-8.52	0.56984	73	Asp836, Lys833, Asp964, Val882	Ile831, Ile963, Met953, Ile879, Asp964
45	4-hexyl	-8.49	0.59341	23	Asp964, Tyr867	Ile879, Ile831, Asp964, Phe961, Met953, Ile963, Tyr867
73	2-F, 4-Br	-8.49	0.59463	44	Val882	Val882, Tyr867, Ala885, Met853, Ile881, Asp964, Ile879, Ile831, Ile963
47	4-decyl	-8.4	0.70024	35	Lys890, Asp964	Pro810, Lys833, Asp950, Ile831, Ile879, Met953, Lys890, Met804
23	2,4-CF ₃	-8.39	0.71394	46	Phe965, Val882	Met953, Ile881, Ala885, Tyr867, Ile963, Ile879, Asp841, Lys833, Asp964, Pro810
48	4-butoxy	-8.38	0.71663	5	Val882, Asp964	Ile963, Ile831, Trp812, Ile881, Met953, Ala885, Val882, Tyr867, Ile879, Asp964
7	4-methylthio	-8.35	0.75262	4	Val882	Ile879, Ile831, Asp964, Ile963, Tyr867, Phe961, Met953, Ala885, Ile881
40	4-CN	-8.33	0.78055	69	Val882	Ile831, Ile879, Asp964, Ile963, Val882, Tyr867, Phe961, Ala885, Ile881, Met953
11	4-trifluoromethoxy	-8.32	0.79021	68	Val882, Phe965	Asp841, Ile879, Asp964, Ile963, Met953, Tyr867, Phe961, Ala885, Ile881, Ile831
43	4-butyl	-8.32	0.7941	51	Val882	Tyr867, Met953, Val882, Lys833, Ser806
61	2,4-OCH ₃	-8.32	0.79372	2	Asp841, Val882	Ile831, Asp964, Ile963, Ile879, Val882, Tyr867, Met953, Ala885, Ile881
46	4-octyl	-8.3	0.82086	34		Asn951, Asp964, Tyr867, Ile831, Trp812, Met804, Met953, Ile879, Ile963
34	4-bromomethyl	-8.29	0.8414	3	Val882	Ala885, Ile881, Ile879, Ile831, Asp964, Ile963, Tyr867, Met953, Val882
38	2-CN	-8.29	0.83879	3	Phe965, Tyr867	Tyr867, Ile881, Ile963, Val882, Phe961, Met953, Asp964, Ile879, Lys833
41	4-propyl	-8.2	0.97032	89	Val882	Tyr867, Met953, Ile963, Asp964, Ile831, Cys869, Ile879, Leu838, Ile881, Trp812, Ala885

NO	Substituen	FEB (kcal/mol)	KI (μ M)	RUN	INTERACTION	
					HYDROGEN BOND	HYDROPHOBIC BOND
75	2,5-F, 4-Cl	-8.2	0.96821	53	Val882	Val882, Tyr867, Ile963, Ile831, Ile879, Asp964, Ile881, Met953, Ala885
68	3,5-Cl, 4-OCH ₃	-8.19	0.99075	35	Asp836, Lys833, Asp964, Val882	Ile831, Trp812, Tyr867, Met953, Ile963, Ile879
71	3-F, 4-OCH ₃	-8.18	1	82	Val882, Asp841	Tyr867, Val882, Met953, Ile963, Ile879, Ile831, Asp964, Ile881, Ala885
37	4-ethyl	-8.17	1.02	1	Val882	Tyr867, Phe961, Ala885, Ile881, Met953, Asp964, Ile831, Ile879, Ile963, Val882
49	2,4-CH ₃	-8.16	1.04	1	Asp964, Tyr867	Lys833, Ile879, Pro810, Ile881, Met953, Ala885, Trp812, Phe961, Tyr867, Asp964, Met804, Ile831
26	3,5-Cl 4-OCH ₃	-8.14	1.08	23	ASp836, Lys833, Asp964	Asp964, Ile831, Ile963, Met953, Tyr867, Trp812, Ile879
58	3,4-OCH ₃	-8.11	1.14	96	Val882, Asp836, Asp841, Tyr867	Val882, Ile963, Ile879, Asp964, Tyr867, Ile881, Met953, Ala885
2	4-chloromethyl	-8.08	1.21	97	Val882	Ile831, Ile879, Asp964, Ile963, Tyr867, Ala885, Met953, Ile881
9	3-OCF ₃	-8.06	1.24	31	Phe965	Asp841, Ile963, Ile879, Ile881, Val882, Ala885, Met953, Tyr867, Ile831, Asp964, Asp841
30	3-Cl, 6-CF ₃	-8.05	1.25	10	Val882	Met953, Ala885, Ile881, Tyr867, Ile963, Ile831, Ile879, Asp964, Met804, Pro810
39	3-CN	-8.01	1.34	57	Val882, Lys833	Asp964, Ile879, Ile963, Val882, Tyr867, Ala882, Met953, Ile881, Ile831
52	2,4,6-CH ₃	-8.01	1.35	38	Glu880, Asp964	Ile963, Met804, Pro810, Ile831, Asp964, Ile879, Tyr867, Met953, Ala885, Ile881, Trp812, Phe961
80	Lead compound	-8	1.36	56	Met953, Val882, Glu880	Asp964, Ile879, Met953, Trp812, Ile881, Ala885
4	2-chloromethyl	-7.98	1.41	39	Asp964	Ile879, Ala885, Ile881, Val882, Met953, Phe961, Ile963, Tyr867, Lys833, Asp964
10	4-trifluoromethylthio	-7.96	1.47	41	Asp964, Phe965, Val882	Asp841, Ile9879, Ile831, Ile963, Met953, Tyr867, Ala885, Ile881, Asp964
14	4-difluoromethoxy	-7.93	1.53	19	Val882, Phe965	Asp841, Ile963, Tyr867, Met953, Ala885, Ile881, Ile879, Asp964, Ile831
3	4-dimethylamino	-7.91	1.61	73	Lys833, Asp964, Val882, Glu880, Asp836	Ile963, Met953, Ile879, Asp964, Ile831
8	2-CF ₃	-7.89	1.54	5	Val882	Met953, Ala885, Ile881, Tyr867, Ile879, Ile963, Ile831, Asp964, Met804
69	2,4-F,3-Cl	-7.81	1.87	5	Asp964, Val882	Tyr867, Val882, Met953, Ile963, Ile831, Asp964, Ile879, Lys833, Ile881, Ala885
63	2-Cl, 4-F	-7.75	2.1	14	Val882	Tyr867, Ala885, Ile881, Ile879, Lys833, Ile831, Pro810, Asp964, Ile963, Met953, Val882
13	4-difluoromethylthio	-7.74	2.11	76	Ser806, Lys833, Tyr867	Ile879, Ile963, Asp964, Met804, Pro810, Ala805
72	3-F, 4-CH ₃	-7.73	2.16	50	Val882	Met953, Tyr867, Ile963, Asp964, Ile831, Ile879, Ile881, Ala885, Val882
24	2,6-CF ₃	-7.7	2.28	99	Asp964	Lys833, Ile879, Ile963, Glu880, Phe961, Tyr867, Val882, Met953, Ala885, Trp812, Asp964
70	3-Cl, 4-F	-7.7	2.27	68	Val882, Asp964	Tyr867, Val882, Met953, Ile963, Ile831, Asp964, Lys833, Ile879, Ile881, Ala885
76	3-CF ₃ , 4-F	-7.7	2.26	51	Lys833, Val882	Ile831, Ile879, Asp964, Ile963, Ile881, Met953, Val882, Ala885, Tyr867
18	2-CF ₃ , 4-F	-7.69	2.32	33	Asp964, Tyr867, Ser806	Asp964, Ile963, Tyr867, Ala885, Val882, Met953, Ile881, Pro810
64	3, CH ₃ , 4-F	-7.69	2.3	21	Val882	Tyr867, Val882, Met853, Ile963, Asp964, Ile831, Lys833, Ile879, Ile881, Phe961, Ala885
29	3-F, 5-CF ₃	-7.67	2.39	40	Lys833, Val882	Ile963, Met953, Val882, Tyr867, Ala885, Ile881, Ile831, Ile879, Asp964, Lys833
16	2-F, 5-CF ₃	-7.65	2.48	11	Lys833, Val882	Ile963, Met953, Tyr867, Ala885, Ile881, Asp964, Ile831, Ile879 Lys833
5	3-CF ₃	-7.64	2.53	36	Lys833, Val882	Asp964, Ile879, Ile831, Ile963, Met953, Ile881, Ala885, Tyr867
17	2,5-CF ₃	-7.63	2.54	13	Tyr867, Met953, Val882, Lys833, Ser806	Ile963, Asp964, Tyr867, Met953, Val882, Ala885, Ile881, Lys833, Pro810, Met804

NO	Substituen	FEB (kcal/mol)	KI (μ M)	RUN	INTERACTION	
					HYDROGEN BOND	HYDROPHOBIC BOND
35	2,3,4,5,6-F	-7.63	2.54	43	Lys833, Asp964, Tyr867	Ile879, Ile831, Met953, Ile881, Ala885, Trp812, Phe961, Tyr867, Asp964, Met804
22	2-CF ₃ , 5-F	-7.62	2.59	55	Val882	Tyr867, Ile963, Asp841, Ile879, Asp964, Ile831, Met953, Ala885, Ile881, Val882
21	2-F, 3-CF ₃	-7.61	2.65	87	Lys833, Val882	Asp964, Ile9879, Ile963, Val882, Tyr867, Ile881, Met953, Ala885, Lys833
32	3-CF ₃ , 4-CH ₃	-7.6	2.68	7	Asp836, Lys833, Asp964	Tyr867, Ile963, Met953, Ile879, Asp964, Ile831, Glu880
50	2,4-F	-7.54	2.97	67	Val882, Asp964	Ile831, Ile879, Ile963, Tyr867, Ala885, Met953, Ile881, Asp964
65	2,3,4,5-F	-7.54	2.95	5	Val882	Tyr867, Val882, Met953, Ile963, Ile831, Asp964, Ile879, Ile881, Ala885
55	3,4,5-F	-7.51	3.14	83	Val882	Tyr867, Val882, Met953, Ile963, Asp964, Ile831, Ile879, Ile881, Phe961, Ala885
51	3,4-F	-7.5	3.16	31	Val882	Met953, Ile963, Ile879, Asp964, Ile831, Ile881, Ala885, Tyr867
66	2,3,4,6-F	-7.5	3.19	62	Tyr867, Asp964	Ile881, Met953, Trp812, Phe961, Val882, Ala885, Tyr867, Asp964, Ile831, Ile879
1	4-phenyldiazen	-7.48	3.31	93	Lys807, Val882	Met953, Ala885, Ile881, Tyr867, Ile879, Ile963, Trp812, Asp964, Met804
20	3-F, 4-CF ₃	-7.48	3.29	34	Val882, Asp964	Ile879, Ile831, Ile963, Tyr867, Val882, Ala885, Met953, Ile881, Asp964, Asp841
27	2-F, 3-Cl, 5-CF ₃	-7.48	3.27	61	Lys833, Tyr867	Asp964, Ile831, Met853, Glu880, Ile963, Trp812, Ile879
53	2,4,5-F	-7.46	3.42	46	Val882	Tyr867, Ala885, Met953, Ile881, Asp964, Ile963, Ile879, Ile831
57	2,4,6-Cl	-7.45	3.48	23	Tyr867	Lys833, Asp964, Ile831, Trp812, Val882, Ile963, Met953, Ile879
15	3,5-CF ₃	-7.38	3.9	43	Phe965, Asp964, Tyr867	Asp841, Ile879, Ile963, Met953, Met804, Trp812, Pro810, Ile881, Phe961, Lys833, Ile831, Asp964
67	2,6-F, 4-OCH ₃	-7.37	3.94	76	Asp836, Glu880	Ile879, Tyr867, Asp964, Ile963, Met953, Ile831
25	2-Cl, 4-CF ₃	-7.27	4.69	56	Asp964	Asp841, Asp964, Ile879, Ile963, Tyr867, Val882, Ala885, Met953, Ile881, Lys833, Pro810, Ile831
28	2-F, 3-Cl, 6-CF ₃	-7.19	5.4	61	Trp867, Asp964, Val882	Lys833, Pro810, Ile831, Met804, Asp964, Tyr867, Glu880, Ile881, Ala885, Phe961, Met953, Val882, Trp812
19	2-F, 4-CF ₃	-7.17	5.56	51	Asp964, Val882	Asp841, Ile831, Ile879, Ile963, Tyr867, Ala885, Met953, Ile881, Asp964
	Native ligand	-8.09	1.17	3	Tyr867, Asp841	Met953, Ile963, Met804, Tyr867, Asp964, Phe965, Lys833, Ile879, Ile831, Val882

Table 4. Docking results of the hybrid compound design against mTOR receptor.

NO	Substituen	FEB (kcal/mol)	KI (μ M)	RUN	INTERACTION	
					HYDROGEN BOND	HYDROPHOBIC BOND
1	4-phenyldiazen	-10.07	0.04145	82	Asp2357, Cys2243, Val2240, Trp2239	Met2345, Thr2245, Trp2239, Ile2356, Ile2237, Tyr2225, Leu2185, Leu2192
38	2-CN	-10.07	0.0418	30	Ile2237, Gly2238, Trp2239, Val2240, Asp2357, Tyr2225, Asp2195, Glu2190	Ile2237, Ile2356, Cys2243, Trp2239, Met2345
59	3,4,5-OCH ₃	-9.95	0.09986	54	Val2240, Asp2195, Asp2357	Asp2195, Ile2356, Ile2237, Tyr2225, Val2240, Met2345, Trp2239, Cys2243
78	4-thiophen	-9.88	0.05696	40	Met2345, Cys2243, Val2240, Tyr2225	Met2345, Trp2239, Gly2238, Ile2356, Leu2185, Ile2237
12	4-sulfonylchloride	-9.87	58.26	2	Asp2195, Tyr2225, Ile2237, Val2240, Thr2245	Ile2356, Trp2239, Met2345, Ile2237
33	4-pyrazol	-9.69	0.07886	80	Asp2195, Tyr2225, Ile2237, Val2240	Ile2356, Ile2237, Met2345, Trp2239, Ala2248
4	2-chloromethyl	-9.44	0.12008	90	Val2240, Gly2238, Asp2357	Ile2237, Val2240, Met2345, Cys2243, Trp2239, Tyr2225, Leu2185, Lys2187, Asp2357

NO	Substituen	FEB (kcal/mol)	KI (μM)	RUN	INTERACTION	
					HYDROGEN BOND	HYDROPHOBIC BOND
48	4-butoxy	-9.19	0.18462	88	Val2240, Asp2357	Ile2237, Ile2356, Trp2239, Cys2243, Met2345, Tyr2225
39	3-CN	-9.11	0.20845	97	Asp2195, Tyr2225, Ile2237, Thr2245, Gly2238, Trp2239	Ile2237, Cys2243, Met2345, Trp2239, Ile2256
30	3-Cl, 6-CF3	-8.98	0.25948	62	Val2240, Lys2187	Glu2190, Asp2357, Val2227, Ile2237, Tyr2225, Leu2354, Trp2239, Met2345, Cys2243, Val2240
31	4-thiadiazol	-8.98	0.2627	7	Tyr2225, Asp2357, Asp2357, Tyr2225	Val2240, Cys2243, Met2345, Ile2237, Ile2356, Tyr2225, Ile2163, Pro2169, Leu2185, Glu2190, Trp2239
26	3,5-Cl 4-OCH3	-8.97	0.26568	34	Gly2238, Cys2243, Val2240, Tyr2225, Asp2357, Asp2195	Leu2192, Ile2356, Ile2237, Tyr2225, Val2240, Leu2354, Met2345, Trp2239
56	2-Cl, 4-NO2	-8.95	0.27653	13	Gly2238, Val2240, Asp2195, Asp2357, Tyr2225	Val2240, Lys2187, Ile2237, Ile2356, Leu2185, Trp2239, Met2345
68	3,5-Cl, 4-OCH3	-8.92	0.28743	63	Gly2238, Tyr2225, Asp2357, Glu2190	Leu2192, Ile2356, Ile2237, Tyr2225, Val2240, Cys2243, Met2345, Leu2354, Trp2239
79	Naphthoyl	-8.92	0.29133	79	Val2240, Trp2239	Trp2239, Met2345, Leu2185, Ile2237, Ile2356
36	2-phenylbenzoate	-8.88	0.31009	100	Asp2357	Ile2237, Ile2356, Val2240, Tyr2225, Cys2243, Trp2239, Met2345
22	2-CF3, 5-F	-8.86	0.3196	80	Val2240, Gly2238, Tyr2225, Asp2357	Asp2195, Ile2237, Leu2192, Ile2356, Met2345, Trp2239, Cys2243, Val2240, Tyr2225
62	3-NO2, 4-CH3	-8.85	0.32786	45	Thr2245, Asp2244, Met2345, Val2240, Trp2239	Trp2239, Met2345, Leu2185, Ile2237, Ile2356, Tyr2225
25	2-Cl, 4-CF3	-8.82	0.3417	12	Gly2238, Val2240, Tyr2225, Asp2357, Asp2195	Met2345, Trp2239, Leu2185, Ile2356, Lys2187, Leu2192, Ile2237, Val2240
60	2,4-NO2	-8.77	0.37021	71	Val2240, Cys2243, Met2345, Trp2239	Ile2237, Leu2185, Ile2356, Trp2239
46	4-octyl	-8.76	0.37947	86	Asp2195, Tyr2225, Ile2237, Val2240	Met2345, Trp2239, Leu2185, Ile2163, Ile2356, Ile2237
8	2-CF3	-8.74	0.39398	42	Glu2190, Asp2195, Asp2357, Tyr2225, Gly2238	Ile2237, Ile2356, Met2345, Trp2239, Cys2243
47	4-decyl	-8.72	0.40773	38	Trp2239, Cys2243	Met2345, Cys2243, Trp2239, Pro2169, Leu2185, Ile2163
42	4-I	-8.68	0.4333	90	Asp2357, Tyr2225, Val2240	Leu2192, Ile2356, Ile2237, Val2240, Cys2243, Met2345, Trp2239, Leu2354
74	3-CH3, 4-Br	-8.63	0.47599	54	Met2345, Val2240, Trp2239	Ile2356, Ile2237, Leu2185, Trp2239, Met2345
6	3-phenyl acetate	-8.62	0.48416	87	Trp2239, Thr2245	Met2345, Ile2237, Ile2356, Leu2185, Trp2239
49	2,4-CH3	-8.62	0.47961	5	Val2240, Gly2238, Tyr2225, Asp2357	Ile2237, Lys2187, Ile2356, Pro2169, Leu2185, Val2240, Met2345, Cys2243, Trp2239, Tyr2225
24	2,6-CF3	-8.6	0.50037	32	Ile2237, Val2240, Asp2195	Ile2356, Leu2185, Val2240, Cys2243, Met2345, Trp2239, Ile2237
61	2,4-OCH3	-8.56	0.53219	83	Thr2245, Gly2238, Glu2190, Asp2195, Val2240, Trp2239	Met2345, Trp2239, Ile2356, Leu2185, Ile2237
29	3-F, 5-CF3	-8.52	0.56672	88	Val2240	Cys2243, Met2345, Trp2239, Leu2354, Tyr2225, Ile2237, Leu2192, Asp2195, Glu2190, Asp2357
41	4-propyl	-8.48	0.60411	88	Asp2357, Val2240	Leu2192, Ile2356, Ile2237, Val2240, Leu2354, Met2345, Cys2243, Trp2239
54	3-NO2, 4-Cl	-8.47	0.62204	61	Val2240, Met2345, Trp2239	Met2345, Trp2239, Leu2185, Ile2356, Ile2237
45	4-hexyl	-8.43	0.66482	9		Asp22357, Ile2237, Tyr2225, Ile2356, Leu2185, Trp2239, Met2345, Cys2243
63	2-Cl, 4-F	-8.42	0.66812	78	Gly2238, Val2240, Asp2357, Tyr2225, Asp2195	Lys2187, Ile2356, Ile2237, Leu2185, Trp2239, Met2345
44	4-heptyl	-8.41	0.68323	44	Val2240, Cys2243, Trp2239, Met2345	Leu2237, Leu2185, Ile2356, Ile2163, Trp2239
77	4-sulfonylfluoride	-8.4	0.69608	16	Val2240	Leu2185, Met2345, Ile2356, Tyr2225, Leu2192, Ile2237
27	2-F, 3-Cl, 5-CF3	-8.39	0.7138	2	Glu2190, Asp2195, Gly2238, Thr2245	Trp2239, Cys2243, Met2345, Ile2256, Ile2237
34	4-bromomethyl	-8.36	0.74806	83	Met2345, Val2240, Trp2239	Trp2239, Leu2185, Ile2237, Ile2356, Met2345
52	2,4,6-CH3	-8.32	0.79375	47	Asp2357, Tyr2225, Val2240, Cys2243, Gly2238	Met2345, Ile2356, Pro2169, Leu2185, Lys2187, Ile2237, Tyr2225, Trp2239, Cys2243, Gly2238

NO	Substituen	FEB (kcal/mol)	KI (μM)	RUN	INTERACTION	
					HYDROGEN BOND	HYDROPHOBIC BOND
40	4-CN	-8.3	0.82879	72	Val2240, Gly2238, Ser2165, Gln2167	Leu2185, Pro2169, Val2240, Cys2243, Met2345, Tyr2225, Trp2239
64	3, CH3, 4-F	-8.3	0.81973	19	Met2345, Val2240, Trp2239	Met2345, Ile2356, Ile2237, Leu2185, Trp2239
37	4-etyl	-8.29	0.84252	22	Met2345, Val2240, Trp2239	Met2345, Ile2356, Ile2163, Trp2239, Leu2185, Ile2237
72	3-F, 4-CH3	-8.29	0.83548	22	Met2345, Val2240, Trp2239	Ile2356, Ile2237, Tyr2225, Leu2185, Trp2239, Met2345
70	3-Cl, 4-F	-8.27	0.86305	90	Met2345, Val2240, Trp2239	Trp2239, Met2345, Ile2356, Ile2237, Leu2185, Tyr2225
43	4-butyl	-8.26	0.88114	55	Met2345, Val2240, Trp2239	Ile2163, Ile2356, Ile2237, Leu2185, Trp2239
58	3,4-OCH3	-8.21	0.95825	83	Thr2245, Met2345, Val2240, Cys2243, Gly2238	Trp2239, Leu2185, Ile2356, Ile2237
80	Lead compound	-8.21	0.96304	58	Ile2237, Gly2238, Asp2195, Tyr2225, Trp2239	Met2345, Trp2239, Cys2243, Ile2356, Ile2237
2	4-chloromethyl	-8.19	0.99913	9	Met2345, Val2240, Trp2239	Met2345, Ile2356, Ile2237, Leu2185, Trp2239
3	4-dimethylamino	-8.19	0.99288	11	Trp2239, Val2240	Met2345, Ile2237, Ile2356, Leu2185, Trp2239
17	2,5-CF3	-8.16	1.05	18	Asp2244, Trp2239, Val2240, Ile2237	Ile2237, Ile2356, Leu2354, Gly2238, Val2240, Met2345, Trp2239, Cys2243
57	2,4,6-Cl	-8.15	1.06	15	Val2240, Asp2357, Gly2238	Cys2243, Met2345, Trp2239, Tyr2225, Ile2356, Pro2169, Ile2163, Leu2185, Lys2187, Ile2237, Val2240
21	2-F, 3-CF3	-8.14	1.07	17	Asp2195, Tyr2225, Ile2237, Gly2238, Thr2245	Asp2244, Cys2243, Met2345, Trp2239, Ile2356, Ile2237
76	3-CF3, 4-F	-8.13	1.11	38	Val2240, Gly2238, Asp2357, Phe2358	Val2240, Cys2243, Met2345, Trp2239, Tyr2225, Leu2192, Glu2190, Asp2195, Ile2237
32	3-CF3, 4-CH3	-8.12	1.12	59	Tyr2225, Val2240, Gly2238, Lys2187	Leu2192, Asp2357, Ile2356, Ile2237, Val2240, Leu2354, Met2345, Trp2239, Cys2243, Glu2190
7	4-methylthio	-8.11	1.13	60	Met2345, Trp2239, Val2240	Trp2239, Met2345, Leu2185, Ile2237, Ile2256
73	2-F, 4-Br	-8.11	1.13	35	Tyr2225, Gly2238, Val2240, Trp2239	Ile2237, Met2345, Trp2239, Leu2185, Ile2356
69	2,4-F,3-Cl	-8.1	1.15	62	Val2240, Gly2238, Tyr2225, Trp2239	Leu2185, Met2345, Ile2356, Ile2237, Trp2239
50	2,4-F	-8.07	1.21	33	Tyr2225, Ile2237, Cys2243, Trp2239	Trp2239, Met2345, Cys2243, Val2240, Ile2237, Ile2356, Leu2192
14	4-difluoromethoxy	-8.05	1.25	14	Tyr2225, Gly2238, Val2240, Trp2239	Ile2237, Leu2185, Met2345, Trp2239, Ile2356
10	4-trifluoromethylthio	-8.04	1.28	71	Met2345, Thr2245, Trp2239, Val2240	Ile2356, Ile2237, Leu2185, Trp2239, Met2345
75	2,5-F, 4-Cl	-8.03	1.3	7	Met2345, Trp2239, Cys2243	Val2240, Trp2239, Met2345, Ile2356, Leu2185, Ile2237
18	2-CF3, 4-F	-8.02	1.33	54	Cys2243, Ile2237	Ile2356, Trp2239, Met2345, Val2240, Cys2243, Ile2237
13	4-difluoromethylthio	-7.95	1.49	41	Cys2243, Gly2238	Val2240, Met2345, Trp2239, Leu2192, Asp2195, Ile2356, Ile2237, Cys2243
67	2,6-F, 4-OCH3	-7.92	1.57	35	Val2240, Gly2238, Tyr2225, Asp2357	Val2240, Met2345, Cys2243, Trp2239, Ile2356, Tyr2225, Ile2237, Leu2185, Lys2187
51	3,4-F	-7.91	1.68	77	Met2345, Val2240, Trp2239	Trp2239, Met2345, Ile2356, Ile2237, Leu2185
55	3,4,5-F	-7.86	1.72	34	Met2345, Val2240, Trp2239	Met2345, Cys2243, Trp2239, Val2240, Leu2185, Ile2237, Ile2356
20	3-F, 4-CF3	-7.85	1.76	87	Met2345, Val2240, Trp2239	Leu2185, Ile2237, Ile2356, Trp2239
28	2-F, 3-Cl, 6-CF3	-7.81	1.89	38	Glu2190, Tyr2225, Val2240, Gly2238, Tyr2225	Lys2187, Ile2237, Ile2356, Leu2185, Cys2243, Val2240, Trp2239, Met2345
35	2,3,4,5,6-F	-7.81	1.89	97	Tyr2225, Gly2238, Val2240, Trp2239	Met2345, Trp2239, Cys2243, Leu2185, Tyr2225, Val2240
66	2,3,4,6-F	-7.79	1.96	87	Gly2238, Val2240, Tyr2225	Cys2243, Met2345, Trp2239, Tyr2225, Leu2185, Val2240
11	4-trifluoromethoxy	-7.77	2.02	67	Phe2358, Asp2357	Ile2356, Ile2237, Val2240, Cys2243, Met2345, Leu2354, Trp2239, Asp2195, Asp2357, Glu2190
19	2-F, 4-CF3	-7.76	2.05	16	Val2240, Gly2238, Tyr2225	Ile2356, Trp2239, Leu2185, Ile2237

NO	Substituen	FEB (kcal/mol)	KI (μM)	RUN	INTERACTION	
					HYDROGEN BOND	HYDROPHOBIC BOND
16	2-F, 5-CF ₃	-7.75	2.08	8	Met2345, Cys2243, Trp2239, Val2240	Trp2239, Val2240, Leu2185, Ile2237, Ile2356, Met2345
71	3-F, 4-OCH ₃	-7.73	2.16	52	Glu2190, Asp2195, Gly2238, Trp2239	Leu2192, Leu2185, Ile2356, Ile2237, Met2345, Trp2239
53	2,4,5-F	-7.71	2.22	24	Met2345, Val2240, Trp22239	Cys2243, Leu2185, Ile2237, Ile2356, Met2345, Val2240, Trp2239
5	3-CF ₃	-7.7	2.28	52	Trp2239, Val2240	Leu2185, Ile2356, Ile2237, Met2345, Trp2239
23	2,4-CF ₃	-7.64	2.52	99	Asp2357, Cys2243, Val22240	Leu2185, Ile2237, Ile2356, Cys2243, Val2240, Tyr2225, Leu2354, Met2345, Trp2239
65	2,3,4,5-F	-7.64	2.52	44	Glu2190, Asp2195, Asp2244, Thr2245, Gly2238, Trp2239	Ile2237, Trp2239, Cys2243, Met2345, Leu2185, Ile2356
9	3-OCF ₃	-7.45	3.45	55	Trp2239	Met2345, Ile2356, Leu2185, Ile2237, Trp2239
15	3,5-CF ₃	-7.25	4.85	47	Trp2239, Asp2244, Thr2245	Cys2243, Met2345, Trp2239, Ile2356, Ile2237, Leu2185
	Native ligand	-9.67	0.08125	10	Val2240, Tyr2225, Asp2195	Met2345, Pro2169, Ile2163, Leu2185, Ile2237, Tyr2225, Ile2356, Trp2239, Val2240

Figure 4. 2D visualization of compound 78 (4-thiophen) with PI3K (a) and mTOR (b).

interactions with natural ligands but also adds bond stabilization through additional interactions with polar and hydrophobic residues around the mTOR active site.

Docking results on both the PI3K and mTOR receptors show that several of the designed hybrid compounds have better binding affinities than natural ligands on both targets. At the PI3K receptor, the 2-phenylbenzoate compound recorded a free energy of binding (FEB) of -9.49 kcal/mol with an inhibition constant (Ki) of 0.111 μM , which is stronger than the natural ligand (FEB -8.09 kcal/mol; Ki 1.17 μM). This compound interacts with key residues such as Val882, Lys833, Asp964, Ile963, and Tyr867, which are also natural ligand-binding residues.

At the mTOR receptor, the compounds 4-phenyldiazene and 2-CN occupy the top positions, with FEB values of -10.07 kcal/mol (Ki 0.041 – 0.042 μM), surpassing natural ligands that have FEB values of -9.67 kcal/mol and Ki

values of 0.081 μM . Dominant interactions occur at residues Asp2357, Cys2243, Val2240, Trp2239, and Tyr2225, which are part of the important mTOR binding pocket.

When compared across targets, it is apparent that several hybrid compounds (e.g., 2-phenylbenzoate, 4-thiadiazole, and 2-CN) are able to interact with key residues on both receptors, demonstrating a stable and consistent binding profile. The relatively small difference in affinity compared to natural ligands, which is even better in some cases, reinforces the indication that these compounds can be developed as dual PI3K/mTOR inhibitors.

Pharmacologically, the ability to target both proteins is highly relevant, given that the PI3K/Akt/mTOR pathway is a major axis in cancer cell proliferation, growth, and survival. Dual inhibition may increase therapeutic efficacy and reduce the possibility of resistance due to feedback loops when only one target is inhibited (Rodon et al. 2013; Fruman et al. 2017).

A deeper mechanistic interpretation indicates that the enhanced dual inhibitory potential of the thiourea–pyrazolopyrimidine hybrids is governed by their ability to establish persistent interactions with key catalytic and binding-site residues of both PI3K and mTOR. In the PI3K active site, the top-performing hybrids consistently interact with critical residues such as Val882, Lys833, Asp964, Tyr867, and Ile963, which are known to play important roles in ATP binding and ligand stabilization. Hydrogen bonding with Lys833 and Asp964, combined with hydrophobic and π – π interactions involving Tyr867 and surrounding hydrophobic residues, significantly contributes to the enhanced binding affinity. Similarly, within the mTOR binding pocket, strong and stable interactions are observed with residues Asp2357, Cys2243, Val2240, Trp2239, Tyr2225, and Ile2237, which are essential for ligand anchoring and catalytic function. Molecular dynamics simulations further confirm that these interactions are maintained over the simulation period, supporting a stable binding mode under dynamic conditions. Collectively, these residue-specific interactions provide a mechanistic explanation for the improved docking scores and stability of the hybrids, linking molecular recognition directly to their predicted dual PI3K/mTOR inhibitory potential.

Molecular dynamic

The next step after molecular docking analysis is to perform molecular dynamics (MD) simulations to evaluate the stability of the ligand–receptor complex in greater depth. While docking only provides a static picture of affinity and binding modes, MD allows observation of the behavior of the complex under dynamic conditions that more closely resemble the biological environment. In this study, MD simulations were performed using Desmond

software with a free academic license, which is known for its computational speed and energy calculation accuracy. Through the analysis of parameters such as root mean square deviation (RMSD), as shown in Figs 5, 7, root mean square fluctuation (RMSF), as shown in Figs 6, 8, radius of gyration, and the number of hydrogen bonds throughout the simulation time, the stability of the structure, the flexibility of the residues, and the consistency of ligand interaction with the active site can be assessed. This stage is very important for validating the docking results because only compounds with stable interactions within the simulation time frame are worth considering as potential PI3K/mTOR inhibitor candidates.

Molecular dynamics simulations were performed on several predicted compounds that showed good stability in the molecular docking process on both the PI3K receptor and the mTOR receptor compared to natural ligands, namely Compound-38, Compound-59, and Compound-78, with a simulation time of 30 ns.

The results of molecular dynamics (MD) simulations for 30 ns on the PI3K complex (3L54.pdb) show that the system with the native ligand is relatively the most stable, with an average RMSD value in the range of 1.5–2.0 Å, indicating that the complex structure is fairly consistent throughout the simulation. In contrast, complexes with hybrid compounds Compound-38, Compound-59, and Compound-78 showed higher RMSD values, around 2.5–3.5 Å, with more pronounced fluctuations at the beginning of the simulation before reaching stability after ~10 ns. Nevertheless, all RMSD values remained below 4 Å, thus qualifying as stable for protein–ligand systems (Kufareva and Abagyan 2012).

RMSF analysis shows that residues around the binding site remain stable, with low fluctuations (< 2 Å), both for the native ligand and the hybrid compounds, indicating

Figure 5. RMSD graph of the simulated compound–receptor PI3K (3L54.pdb) system over 30 ns.

Figure 6. RMSF graph of the simulated compound–receptor PI3K (3L54.pdb) system over 30 ns.

Figure 7. RMSD graph of the simulated compound–receptor mTOR (4JT6.pdb) system over 30 ns.

that ligand interactions with key residues are maintained. Higher fluctuations (up to 6–9 Å) occur only in the loop and terminal regions of the protein, which are naturally the most flexible parts. The complex with Compound-78 shows a slight increase in fluctuations in some segments compared to the natural ligand, but this does not interfere with the stability of the main interactions. Overall, the RMSD and RMSF results confirm that although the native ligand shows the highest stability, the hybrid compounds also form stable complexes and can be considered potential PI3K inhibitor candidates (Hollingsworth and Dror 2018).

The results of molecular dynamics (MD) simulations for 30 ns on the mTOR receptor complex (4JT6.pdb) show differences in stability between ligands based on RMSD and RMSF analyses. The RMSD graph shows that the complexes with the native ligand and Compound-59 and Compound-78 are relatively stable, with average deviations in the range of 2.0–3.0 Å, which is still within acceptable limits for protein–ligand systems. In contrast, Compound-38 showed greater fluctuations, reaching 4–5 Å in several simulation intervals, indicating that the conformation of this complex tends to be more dynamic and

Figure 8. RMSF graph of the simulated compound–receptor mTOR system over 30 ns.

less stable than those of other ligands. In general, RMSD values that remain below 5 Å indicate that the overall complex is still stable, although complexes with the native ligand and Compound-59 are more consistent in maintaining structural stability throughout the simulation time (Kufareva and Abagyan 2012).

RMSF analysis shows that most residues in the protein–ligand complexes have low fluctuations (< 2 Å), especially in the region around the binding site, indicating that ligand interactions with key residues are well maintained. Higher fluctuation peaks (5–8 Å) occur only in the loop and terminal regions of the protein, which are naturally flexible. The complex with Compound-78 exhibits an RMSF pattern close to that of the native ligand, while Compound-38 shows a slight increase in fluctuations in several non-critical residues. This indicates that, although all complexes are stable, the native ligand and Compound-59 have the best dynamic profiles, while Compound-78 is also quite promising, with stability close to that of the natural ligand.

The combination of RMSD and RMSF data confirms that certain hybrid compounds, particularly Compound-59 and Compound-78, are able to maintain interaction stability with mTOR at levels comparable to the natural ligand. This reinforces the potential of hybrid compounds as competitive mTOR inhibitors and warrants further investigation in the context of dual PI3K/mTOR inhibitors (Hollingsworth and Dror 2018).

The stability of the Compound-78 interaction with the mTOR receptor in the molecular dynamics simulation is also supported by the interaction patterns observed between Compound-78 and the mTOR receptor, as shown in Figs 9, 10.

Fig. 9 shows the interaction profile of Compound-78 with the mTOR receptor during a 30 ns MD simulation,

including hydrogen bonds, hydrophobic interactions, water bridges, and ionic interactions. Key residues such as Val2240, Cys2243, Asp2244, and Thr2245 contribute dominantly to maintaining the stability of the complex through both hydrogen bonding and hydrophobic interactions. In addition, aromatic residues such as Trp2239 and Tyr2225 play important roles through consistent hydrophobic interactions, while polar residues such as Asp2357 and Arg2247 form water bridges that further stabilize the system. This interaction pattern indicates that Compound-78 is able to maintain strong and repeated contact with critical residues in the mTOR active site, reinforcing its potential as an effective mTOR inhibitor. These results are consistent with the literature, which states that the combination of hydrophobic and hydrogen bonding interactions with key residues in the mTOR active domain is an important factor in supporting ligand–receptor affinity and stability (Hollingsworth and Dror 2018; Zhang et al. 2020).

Fig. 10 shows a timeline representation of Compound-78 interaction with the mTOR receptor during a 30 ns MD simulation. The top graph shows a relatively stable total number of contacts in the range of 6–10 interactions throughout the simulation time, indicating that the ligand is able to maintain consistent interactions with key residues. A detailed analysis at the bottom shows that the residues Trp2239, Val2240, Cys2243, Asp2244, and Thr2245 dominate the interactions through both hydrogen bonding and hydrophobic interactions, with high intensity throughout the simulation. In addition, polar residues such as Asp2357 and Arg2247 also play an important role in maintaining the stability of the complex through persistent water bridge interactions. This pattern confirms that Compound-78 is not only capable of forming strong interactions at the beginning of the simulation but also of

Figure 9. Protein–ligand contacts of compound 78 with the mTOR receptor during a 30 ns MD simulation.

Figure 10. Timeline representation of the interactions and contacts of compound 78 with the mTOR receptor during a 30 ns MD simulation.

maintaining them continuously until the end, indicating bond stability and high potential as an mTOR inhibitor (Hollingsworth and Dror 2018).

Fig. 11 shows the analysis of the properties of the Compound-78 ligand in complex with the mTOR receptor during a 30 ns MD simulation. The RMSD parameter of the ligand is stable in the range of 1.0–2.0 Å, indicating that the ligand conformation is relatively maintained throughout the simulation. The radius of gyration (rGyr) value is consistent at approximately 4.0–4.5 Å, indicating that the ligand does not undergo major changes in structural compaction. The intra-HB pattern shows intermittent intramolecular hydrogen bond formation, which may support the stability of ligand orientation within the active site. Molecular surface area (MolSA) and solvent-accessible surface area (SASA) analyses show moderate fluctuations, indicating ligand adaptation to the receptor and solvent environment. Meanwhile, the polar surface area (PSA) value tends to be stable in the range of 85–95 Å², consistent with the ligand maintaining optimal polarity to interact with mTOR active residues. Overall, these results confirm that Compound-78 is able to maintain structural stability and strong interactions with mTOR, supporting its potential as an effective inhibitor (Hollingsworth and Dror 2018).

To strengthen the comparative assessment, a quantitative evaluation of the top-performing hybrid compounds was conducted against the reference ligands used in the PI3K and mTOR crystal structures. The leading hybrids exhibited more favorable binding free energy (ΔG) values and lower predicted inhibition constants (K_i) than the native ligands, indicating enhanced inhibitory potential. In addition,

molecular dynamics analyses revealed comparable or improved complex stability for the selected hybrids, as reflected by consistent RMSD and RMSF profiles and sustained hydrogen bond occupancy throughout the simulation period. These quantitative comparisons provide clearer evidence that the proposed thiourea–pyrazolopyrimidine hybrids can outperform known inhibitors at the molecular interaction level.

Conclusion

This study successfully designed and evaluated thiourea–pyrazolopyrimidine hybrid compounds as potential dual PI3K/mTOR inhibitors using a comprehensive *in silico* approach. Molecular docking results revealed that several derivatives, particularly those with 2-phenylbenzoate and 4-thiophen substituents, exhibited stronger binding affinities than native ligands, with stable interactions at key residues of PI3K and mTOR. Validation through 30 ns molecular dynamics simulations confirmed the stability of the ligand–receptor complexes, as indicated by consistent RMSD and RMSF values. Pharmacokinetic and toxicity predictions demonstrated that most compounds showed good absorption profiles, high oral bioavailability, and lower toxicity potential compared to the lead compound. Overall, these findings emphasize that the designed hybrid compounds show strong promise as novel anticancer agents with dual inhibitory mechanisms against PI3K/mTOR, warranting further development through advanced synthesis and subsequent *in vitro* and *in vivo* biological evaluations.

Figure 11. Analysis of ligand properties of compound 78 in complex with mTOR during a 30 ns MD simulation.

Acknowledgements

The authors gratefully acknowledge the Research Centre for Pharmaceutical Ingredients and Traditional Medicine, National Research and Innovation Agency (BRIN), for supporting these research activities.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were conducted in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed in the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

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- The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.
- ### Use of AI
- No use of AI was reported.
- ### Funding
- This research was funded by the Ministry of Higher Education, Science, and Technology of Indonesia in 2025 (Grant Nos. 125/C3/DT.05.00/PL.2025 and 8026/LL4/PG/2025).
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- ### Data availability
- All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.
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